

TECHNICAL FUNCTIONS OF DESIGN AND ENGINEERING ACTIVITIES

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Annotation

The article discusses the technical functions of the design and engineering activities of future engineers. The introduction of BIM Design technology – Building Information Modeling (building information modeling) in the construction industry. The task of developing design competence in the training of future engineers is also considered. The introduction of digital technologies represents an important step towards a modern and interactive form of education in the field of construction.

Keywords

Design and engineering activities, Building Information Modeling, functions, digital educational environment, research, system engineering

A separate change in engineering activities in the construction sector occurred due to the introduction of BIM Designing technology – Building Information Modeling (building information modeling). This technology represents a revolutionary approach to the organization of design and production of buildings, aimed at the analysis, processing and processing of information about buildings (information modeling in construction), providing for the storage of information about construction sites from their design to disposal.

One of the problems of implementing building information modeling is the problem of a shortage of qualified engineering personnel, one of the solutions to which is to create a “modern and secure digital educational environment”. Thus, professional problems are a stimulating element of educational change.

Following the established logic of the presentation of the study, we proceed to consider the functions of engineering activities.

In addition to the concepts of engineering activity in the analysis of research, O.O.Gorshkova, Ye.B.Yerskina, D.D.Iskhakova, S.I.Osipova, Yu.B.Sveshnikova and other scientists identify the following areas:

and technical, social and managerial (D.D.Iskhakova) [3];

- analytical, opera-research, design, organizational and technological (Ye.B.Yerskina, S.I.Osipova) [2; 4];

-research, scientific tional, synthetic (O.O.Gorshkova) [1];

-technician-user, technician-manufacturer (design, invention, construction, etc.)) (Yu.B.Sveshnikova) [5].

Summarizing the presented and other classifications of design and engineering functions, we distinguish the following two blocks of functions: social and technical. Social functions include humanistic, socio-economic, managerial, educational and developmental. As part of the dissertation research, the technical functions presented in Figure 1 are of interest.

1- drawing. Technical functions of design and engineering activities

Design-the function is to implement a technical idea in the form of a technical project by designing with the help of technical means.

Design - the function is to develop a technical system for the implementation of the project, in which the technical idea is implemented in the form of drawings of a working draft.

The analysis and technical assessment function allows you to identify trends and prospects for technical development and determine the main parameters of an engineering task.

On the other hand, the research function manifests itself in the study of a technical problem in accordance with scientific laws.

The technological function is manifested in the development of a technical system for creating a technical object.

The function of conducting production is to organize production and coordinate the joint activities of personnel to solve a particular technical problem.

Operation and repair function The operation performs the maintenance of the facility in working condition.

The system design function developed in engineering and led to the emergence of a new engineering profession - system engineering. Its meaning is to give the entire cycle of engineering actions a single direction, an integrated character and is the methodological basis for the formation and use of information systems in construction organizations.

The study of the above engineering functions indicates that a significant part of the technical functions of engineering consists of design and construction.

Summarizing the above, we will analyze the concept of engineering activity as a special type of professional activity of an engineer, which includes engineering content and functions that require a systematic assignment to the subject of activity.

The systemic functioning of engineering activities is determined by the engineering design process itself. The engineering content of modern engineering activities is focused on the changes taking place in the field of engineering and technology, while a significant role is assigned to design activities in the implementation of changes.

Based on the analyzed definition of engineering activity, its essence is revealed, which requires an engineer to have a systematic understanding of the design object, that is, the presence of a specially formed, scientific platform for engineering thinking, engineering language and engineering image in the form of drawings, knowledge of modern automatic design systems, communication skills, etc.

Indeed, analyzing the educational process, its content, forms, methods and means, the impact on the process of training specialists at the present stage of development of society and scientific and technological progress, we found that the need for design and engineering activities of future engineers is determined by:

Firstly, socio-economic development requires updating the education system, methods and technologies of the educational process. Innovations in the design activity of a future engineer in such a process generate the need to develop creative thinking and design competencies.

Secondly, designing the content of education requires the search for new organizational forms, learning technologies, that is, the introduction of innovations in education.

Thirdly, the development of motivational-value, creative-activity and operational-technological competencies of future engineers in relation to mastering design knowledge, skills, and their application in practice expresses the social, pedagogical and psychological relevance of the research problem.

The task of developing design competence in the training of future engineers, first of all, the disclosure of the essence of this concept, the definition of its structural structure, requires the establishment of patterns, principles, conditions and directions of the competence approach in the process of vocational training.

Based on the analysis of research on improving the process of training future engineers in the bachelor's degree 60730300 – construction engineering in higher education institutions: the construction of buildings and structures, as well as the analysis of the qualification requirements of the educational direction, educational regulations, curricula and programs, it is established that the urgent task in the training of future engineers is to solve the following important issues:

1) comparison of indicators of the components of the readiness of future engineers for design activities.

2) determination of the levels of competence development for the introduction and application of innovative technologies in design and engineering activities.

3) organization, conduct and implementation of experimental testing works that determine the level of development of design competence of future engineers.

References:

1. Горшкова, О.О. Исследовательская деятельность как неотъемлемый компонент профессиональной подготовки будущего инженера / О.О. Горшкова // Известия высших учебных заведений. Поволжский регион. Гуманитарные науки. - 2013. - № 2 (26). - С. 169-176.

2. Ёерскина, Ёе.Б. Содержанийе компетентностной модели выпускника с квалификацией «бакалавр» (на примере направления подготовки 270800 Строительство) / Ё.Б. Ерскина // Стандарты и мониторинг в образовании. 2012. - № 3. - С. 54-59.

3. Исхакова, Д.Д. Взаимосвязь характера деятельности и содержания подготовки инженера / Д.Д. Исхакова, Д.Н. Маликова, В.Р. Гатинская и [др.] // Вестник казанского технологического университета. - 2012. - С. 272-276.

4. Осирова, С.И. Компетентностный подход в реализации инженерного образования / С.И. Осирова // Педагогика. - 2016. - № 6. - С. 53-60.

5. Свешникова, Ю.Б. Методологические основы культуры инженерии и тенденции её функционирования / Ю.Б. Свешникова // Вестник Воронежского государственного университета. Серия: Лингвистика и межкультурная коммуникация. - 2008. - №3. - С. 220-225.

